

DEVELOPING GLOBAL BRAND BUILDING MODEL IN MANAGEMENT EDUCATION

Achutha Jois

Indian Institute of Management Kashipur
Kundeshwari, Kashipur, Uttarakhand, India
Email: achutha.efpm2016@iimkashipur.ac.in

Somnath Chakrabarti

Indian Institute of Management Kashipur
Kundeshwari, Kashipur, Uttarakhand, India
Email: somnath.chakrabarti@iimkashipur.ac.in

Received: 2021-08-05

Accepted: 2021-10-06

Published online: 2021-11-07

Abstract

Higher education has changed irrevocably with the advent of globalization, internet technologies and modern methods of learning. Educators' thought process is undergoing a sea of change along with transition towards education brand building. Most of the branding frameworks focus on logo design, style and look & feel rather than covering deeper aspects of building a global brand. This study aims to cover broader aspects of global education brand building from the student perspective and identify key issues emerging economy management institutes face while building a global brand. Mixed method approach was adopted to delve deep into issues in building global management education brands from emerging economies. Open-ended unstructured interviews with 18 education experts resulted in the identification of key attributes and antecedents, also validated with a structured literature review. The extensive literature search resulted in more than one thousand academic research papers, while the structured approach selected 107 peer-reviewed academic articles. This study used quantitative methods with random sampling as the main methodology and utilized structured equation modeling to develop the model. This study's key research findings are that prospective students look at immigration to western countries, global opportunities, and globally recognizable education brands as top reasons while selecting education institutes for their higher education needs. This study's generalizability is fairly limited; however, the model can be extrapolated to other fields to test its validity. This paper brings out a branding framework and global brand-building model for higher education management brands.

Keywords: Education Services Marketing, Global Brand Building, Global Marketing, Student Choice making.

1. Introduction

Education has changed irrevocably with the advent of globalization, internet and modern methods of learning. Educator dilemma has changed with changing times; education brands have undergone a sea of change due to intense competition. Globalization of markets (Levitt, 1983) is pushing western education brands to go global. Brands in respective countries have started coming under pressure due to the expansion of western brands globally (Dawar, Frost, 1999).

Another perennial question is, can smaller local brands with limited funding survive global brands' onslaught. States have spent a significant amount of money and effort on higher education (Delaney, Doyle, 2011) by creating massive infrastructure, but the critical question is, can the state keep spending on higher education endlessly (Martin et al., 2015). Western education brands are also taking the pedagogy, education systems & methods to global markets with little localization for respective markets, some of the key examples are Harvard Business School™, INSEAD™, London School of Business, MIT Sloan School of Management (Wilkins et al., 2018). Globalization of education is also bringing in opportunities for brands from emerging markets that have unique capabilities. This study has tried to identify key attributes about building a global brand, thereby arriving at a theoretical framework for management education brands. The focus of the study has been emerging economy management education brands that want to go global.

Traditionally brands distinguishing factor in the marketplace has been logo, design, style, sound, symbol and promise (AMA, 2017). Branding is a key marketing tool to create sustainable differentiating factors to compete in the marketplace by creating a long-lasting impression in the minds of consumers, as in this case in the minds of the student community. Higher education institutes' campus architecture, website, and compendium documents address the human sensory experience of sight (Hulten, 2017). Prospective students look at pedagogical content, program structure, greenery at campus, and physical touch points such as classrooms which address the sensory organ of touch (Hulten, 2017). Higher education institutes' intense student engagement programmes lead to satisfied students and alumni, resulting in positive word of mouth. Brand promises of higher education institutes reflect ethos, values, mission, and objectives. Brand building (Chapleo, 2015) starts with professing delivery commensurate with the brand promise aided by intense student engagement pre-admission and post graduating from campus.

1. Literature Review

This study has adopted extensive literature research (LR) to understand various perspectives on branding, student consumer perceptions and student experiences. This study selected most journals from bibliographic (Justin, Alex, 2020) databases such as WoS (Web of Science), Scopus, and most of the literature searches on journal aggregators like Open Athens, EBSCO, Elsevier and Emerald. Further structured literature review (SLR) was conducted based on selections in peer-reviewed ABDC (Australian Business Dean Council) journals, Association of Business Schools (ABS), Journal Quality List (JQL with minimum 3-star ranking) between 1902 till 2020. SLR focused on identifying base papers and theoretical background for each of the key attributes emanating from literature. Research journal search based on keywords, base theories, concepts resulted in the selection of articles as shown in Table 1, further structured selection of journals based on the quality of content resulted in the selection of 322 academic peer-reviewed articles, detailed analysis of each of these articles resulted in the selection of 107 important papers.

Table 1. Structured literature search and selection

Search keywords	N (Articles)	Key selected journals	Articles after screening
Student needs & wants	286	56	32
Education brand building	278	32	17
Student attitude and perception	385	24	21
Campus & infrastructure in education institutes	142	12	28
Academic activities, initiatives, stimulus, environment	562	39	39
Student choice making and selection process	840	39	24
Culture at campus, events at campus	899	16	37
Brand awareness, trust, promise, identity, experience, trust, equity, loyalty, recognition, satisfaction	4653	81	124

This study has highlighted various theoretical backgrounds that address fundamental concepts related to branding and basic attributes that play a key role in building a brand after analyzing the selected articles. Each identified attribute got validated with select academicians & deans of business schools. In the beginning, this study also used both unstructured and structured questionnaire methods while interviewing 18 subject experts in education branding, vice-chancellors, marketing professors, academicians, especially those who have decades of experience in professing and running successful education brands. The majority of the educators highlighted student perception, student attitude, student experience, campus infrastructure, and student loyalty as key factors in building a long-term sustainable brand. The attributes that emanated from the exploratory research are again validated using the structured literature review approach to identify the theoretical background.

This study used the 'Likert scale' for each attribute, which is explained later in this article.

The literature review work begins with understanding perspectives of western brands going global. This study tries to define 'West' by quoting Turner, Ross (1893, 1902), which defines 'West' as not just an area but a condition; it is the region where the influence of free land is transforming ideas of older societies and institutions of yesteryear. Higher education brands are predominantly dominated by western economies with skewed market share and significant mind share among the global student community. Harvard Business School, Stanford University, Wharton, MIT, London Business School, INSEAD (France, Abu Dhabi, Singapore), HEC Paris, Stanford, University of Chicago have attracted significant global student talent share. The western higher education management brands have experimented with various pedagogies, teaching/learning methods, education systems over a period of time to achieve global recognition (Ilie et al., 2020); however, lately, western brands are encountering market competition from emerging economy brands.

In the EU (European Union) higher education context, markets are becoming tougher, business schools are in intense competition, management or educators, including faculty & staff, programs, processes, strategy has to evolve from where they are to adapt to the new world (Jurse, 2011). As per QS Global MBA Rankings 2019 report, Stanford followed by Harvard are sharing top 2 rankings, INSEAD is ranked 6th with multiple campuses at Fontainebleau & Singapore, EU Business School Ranked 100+ is located in Barcelona, Geneva, Montreux & Munich, UIBS campuses are at Zurich, Antwerp, Barcelona, Brussels (QS Global MBA Rankings, 2019). Similarly, Harvard, INSEAD, Stanford is trying to enter the global arena with localized management programmes such as the Stanford Graduate School of business seed transformation programme in Chennai, India, Harvard leadership management development programmes in Mumbai, MIT Sloan general management programmes in India. Emerging economy management education brands are in the process of going global with global campuses such as SP Jain Dubai, Singapore, Sydney, BITS Pilani Dubai campus, IMT Dubai campus, IIM Bangalore programme in 5 leading global cities, Symbiosis, Assumption & Asian Institute of Technology from Thailand, University of Malaya & Limkokwing from Malaysia and UGM and ITB of Indonesia. Higher education brands from emerging economies have always adapted and adopted the western management education system to local markets to address aspiring student needs (Ilie et al., 2020). Emerging economy brands have always found it tough to compete with their global peers due to the perception that the United States, Europe, and Japan brands are symbols of high quality and value (Bartlett, Ghoshal, 2000).

Globalization leads to the growth of emerging economies, thus fuelling the aspirations of the student community in emerging economies, in turn energizing the emerging brands of management education to look beyond local markets for student talent. Educator dilemma pertains to taking their education system global, which appeals to the global student community. Dao and Thorpe (2015) and Gatfield et al. (1999) highlight those Australian universities' international promotional strategies brought out four key factors: academic instruction, recognition, campus life, and guidance. 'CIPP' model (context, input, process and product) has been suggested for performance evaluation of higher education institutions (Chinta et al., 2016). This research study focused on problematization (Stone, 2012, Foucault's 1984 interview), identifying areas of inquiry to transform challenges into research questions. This article analyses problems from multiple education sectors while identifying challenges faced by emerging economy education brands.

1.1 Education Brands in Modern Context

Higher education brands have to go beyond their traditional branding boundaries to take on fast emerging global competition. Brands from emerging economies with strong local geographical presence have to move beyond their comfort zone as international brands, especially from the west, have started entering their local turf (Jurse, 2011). Educators have to create genuine differentiators using pedagogy, programs, engagement, and brands in the academic context. The branding idea is explained along with ways of creating differentiations using positioning; however, brand credibility is built on delivering brand promise and exceeding the brand expectations, as discussed in the following sections in this article. Increasing competitive practices in the international higher education market calls for academic market research in consumer behaviour and student motivations. This research work focuses on differences in international students' behavioural motivations while choosing universities (Gatfield, Chen, 2006). This study has also used Fishbein, Ajzen (1975) multi-attribute 'Theory of Planned Behaviour' model to understand student motivations by using samples from Taiwanese and Chinese students who want to study in USA, UK, and Australia.

2.2 Understanding Consumer Behaviour from Students' Perspective (Needs & Wants)

This article also outlines work done on self, extended self and try to identify gaps in the previous works (Gatfield, Chen, 2006, Ahmad et al., 2016, Dao, Thorpe, 2015, Keller and Kevin, 1993, Aaker, 1991, Ya-Hsin et al., 2014, Hsia, 1988) to develop newer theories and models. This article provides evidence with its constraints so that any researcher can extend the work to test the theory or model in their context. Students choosing to move overseas for their higher education needs have significantly increased in the last few decades resulting in significant scholarly attention towards this subject (Ahmad et al., 2016). As Dao, Thorpe (2015) research work brings out factors

that influence Vietnamese students while they make university choices, the factors in descending order of importance are facilities and services, programme, price, offline information, opinion, online information, ways of communication, programme additions and advertising. Emerging economies universities should carefully adopt marketing insights from research work based on context not just because it is a comparable brand; however, it should also invite research scholars to measure further and test the associations between the factors as independent variables and a solid choice as dependent variables (Dao and Thorpe, 2015).

2.3 Student Experience Pre and Post Purchase Leading To Perception towards Brand

The prestige of the school (recognition of a brand) may not rate higher when compared to the choice of location made by students while selecting universities. Most research work focuses on students studying in western countries even though a considerable number of overseas students are studying in emerging economy higher education institutes (Cova and Bernard, 1997 and Ahmad et al., 2016). Many states funded universities of emerging economies do not get sufficient financial support and autonomy needed in a competitive global education scenario (Martin et al., 2015). Educators have to look at students' perception towards academic studies, pedagogy, student preparedness, the idea of engagement, academic fraternity networking, societal & stakeholder expectations, availability of access to the body of knowledge, competition in the realistic world, past expectations & precedence, alumni influences & word of mouth spread, individualistic need and influence by media such as SMAIT (social media, Apps, Internet and Technology). The same can be proven by OEM (Orientation Evaluation Matrix) defined by James A Muncy (2008) with column headings as faculty input, student input, stakeholder input, and row headings as content, pedagogy, curriculum, rigor, and use of student evaluations. After studying Anil & Icli (2013) research work, educators can say that academic quality is defined by pedagogy, teaching quality, curriculum, learning rigour, career opportunities and student readiness.

Student loyalty or alumni loyalty, or word of mouth are directly related to student satisfaction (Riccardo et al., 2017) at the Institution or University, support services at the facility, as student satisfaction increases loyalty as well increases but educators need not assume that all satisfied students' customers are loyal. The key question is whether student loyalty is directly proportional to student satisfaction. Many students may say flexibility towards pedagogy, curriculum, rigor, evaluation, and grading may lead to more satisfaction and thus loyalty, and then should educators make everything flexible to suit the needs & expectations of the students.

Chinta et al. (2016) and Ramzan (2015) highlight that since the establishment of the Bologna accord and European association for quality assurance (ENQA) in 2000, European higher education brands have accepted a four-stage model of evaluation for quality assurance of their universities, namely, self-evaluation reports, external peer review with a site visit, writing report and publication by evaluation committee followed up by a report by quality agencies. Student consumer value and brand image can be created based on five human senses based on multi-sensory brand experience strategy (Hulten, 2017), leading to brand equity resulting in brand loyalty. Student loyalty scale should consider customer switching behaviour aspects, word of mouth, program cost, core service failure, service encounters, competition (Ohmae, 1982), service response, and ethical issues vital to brand recognition among global students community.

2.4 Student Attitude towards Management Education Brands

This study has used the "MODEL" framework proposed by Fazio (1986), wherein anybody attitude can be defined in two different ways, namely explicit measure and implicit measure. Explicit measures of attitude are at conscious levels, which are articulated with deliberate intentions. Implicit measures of attitude will be at unconscious levels, or subconscious levels articulated involuntarily and unknown as well. The 'Theory of Reasoned Action' (TRA) was developed by Fishbein and Ajzen (1967) and further improved in 1975 based on social psychology, persuasion models and attitude theories. TRA was later expanded by Martin Fishbein and Icek Ajzen in 1980, 1985 to the 'Theory of Planned Behaviour' (TPB) and 'Reasoned Action Approach' (RAA) that mainly focuses on the intention of an action rather than whether they perform such action or not. Motivation and opportunity items coupled with the Likert scale can be used to prepare the questions pertaining to this measure. Four factors play a key role in selecting an international institute for their higher education needs, namely, country attractions with the prospect of better employment & higher salary, the image of the institution (brand) & recognition of educational qualification globally, learning experiences, and word of mouth (Ahmad et al., 2016).

Gatfield and Chen study (2006) had the limitation of focusing on Australia, UK and USA as countries of destination. The last decade has seen female students' enrolment in higher education institutes have increased significantly; however, female students differ while selecting the higher education institute (Sim et al., 2020). The research was on one specific country and should be extended to multi-group analysis from different countries. Student motivations to study in international branches of universities are a combination of various push-pull factors such as institution brand standing in the international market, academic reputations, marketability of the degrees, cost of studies compared to home country cost, cost of living in the host city, safety at universities while staying at the city, cultural proximity, attractiveness attributes and location convenience (Ahmad and Buchanan, 2015).

2.5 Effect of Campus Infrastructure Scalability in Building Brands

This study has tried to adapt the measures (scale) from the Information Technology infrastructure field as there were not enough scale development papers on infrastructure scalability. Hesham and Mustafa (2005) define scalability in multiple dimensions. This study has adapted the five different dimensions (scales) to the field of study, namely, 'administrative scalability', 'functional scalability', 'geographic scalability', 'load scalability' and 'generation scalability'. This study has combined the first and fourth scales while adapting for this research objective. The scales which can be used are as follows facilities & ability to expand (administrative & load), academic scalability (functional), place (geographic), intake of the newer generation of students, heterogeneous campus.

2.6 Selection Mechanism Impact on Campus Culture

In ancient India, Gurukul (Monastery) system of education, ancient gurus (teachers) employed a unique selection mechanism, their initial part of education mainly focused on the selection, instructors can quote various stories (case studies) of Panchatantra wherein Guru Vishnu Sharma employed to select as well teach his students. This study had to refer to various research works to define the selection. Teng and Ssu-yu (1943) say that Chinese civil servant exams established in AD605 may be the first documented modern selection tests, which may have influenced subsequent examination systems, so educators can assume that selection was always given importance in education. This study has tried to adapt the selection mechanism variable measure from the field of Human Resources. These requirements for the selection system are characteristics known as KSAOs (knowledge, skills, ability, and other characteristics, Teng and Ssu-yu, 1943), which can also be used as scale items coupled with the 'Likert scale'. This study has thus come with the below measures to define selection mechanism, personality, cognitive ability, scholarly & reasoning, psychometric, biographical historical data, physical ability, skills & work sample, aptitude & knowledge and interviews.

2.7 Academic Stimulation of Students at Campus

This study has tried to refer to the scales or measures developed by Goff, Maynard, and Ackerman (1992), wherein typical intellectual engagement (TIE) is a construct based on personality also can be referred to as a person's like or dislike of intellectually demanding activities. Academic performance was defined by Von Stumm et al. (2011), Woo et al. (2007) say that TIE is hard to distinguish from the earlier construct need for cognition and is positively correlated with openness to experience as referred by Ackerman et al. (1994). Chinta et al. (2016), Kirkpatrick (1994) evaluation model brings out an outcome-based approach for measuring the effectiveness of higher education brands. These can be applied to institutions that are interested in results.

This model uses four components, reaction, learning, behaviour and results; and similarly, 'CIPP' model for evaluating higher education institutes uses Drewes, Michael (2006) used rank-ordered 'logit model' to explore how a student makes choices between universities. Logit model study showed that applicants appear to be attracted to universities that offer higher levels of academic quality.

2.8 Student Perception, Culture, Satisfaction and Loyalty towards Education Brands

Perception is the identification, interpretation and organization of what is observed through sensory organs to understand the presented information (Schacter et al., 2011). Three components of perception are 'perceiver', 'target', 'being', and three factors that can influence perceptions: experience, motivational state, and emotional state (Alan and Gary, 2011). This study adopted a scale to come out with perception measures: learning, memory, expectation, attention, and situation. Chinta et al., (2016) research work share nine perspectives of metrics and benchmarks to evaluate international universities. The benchmarks are internal, external and aspirational referencing, and metrics are input, process and output.

Culture in any university depends upon the campus bonding between students that is nurtured over a period of time at the campus. This study has extensively researched the scales for culture, especially on-campus culture, thereby adopting the scales from organizational studies and human resources studies. This study has adopted the scale items which are based on OCP (Organizational Cultural Profile) model developed by O'Reill et al. (1991) that says the belief that makes distinctions based on eight categories, namely, innovation, supportiveness, stability, respect for people, outcome orientation, attention to detail, team orientation, and aggressiveness.

This study referred to the works of various researchers on 'satisfaction' to adopt the measures and scales, especially items and point scale from Berry, Leonard, Parasuraman (1991) that provides the satisfaction gap between objective and quantitative measurement of satisfaction. Kessler (2003) proposed a survey for customer satisfaction measures based on the 'Likert scale'. The level of satisfaction may vary based on other products against which the student consumers can compare the current offerings in the education sector. This study adopted the measures (items) and scale gap, attitude, and perception from the aforementioned research work.

This study adapted the scales for loyalty from marketing studies wherein extensive research has happened on brand loyalty (Tina, 2016). This study looked for a measure closer to the research work, referred to Reichheld (1996), one of the thought leaders on brand loyalty. Association between customer loyalty and financial outcomes is not straightforward; student loyalty needs to be understood without overspending on loyalty, student as customers is becoming lesser sensitivity to cost (Werner and Kumar,

2002). Long term repeat customers are comparatively less price-sensitive, and it is tough for them to stop using and suggesting the brand to others, thus resulting in word of mouth. Student consumers tend to be more loyal to higher education institutes, and it is essential to identify key attributes that influence the decision to be loyal; some of the key attributes which came out from research work are perceived quality, satisfaction, emotional commitment and trust (Fabio et al., 2012). The scales used are student perceived value, brand trust, student satisfaction, word of mouth, repeat purchase behaviour, and commitment. Student loyalty depends on effective communication, the institution's legacy, institutions internal models of culture building and sustenance that result in higher engagement with stakeholders.

2.9 Brand Identity

Brand identity can be defined as the combination of multi-dimensional factors like brand logo design, symbols representing a brand, packaging, product performance, service quality, brand image, brand associations with consumers (students in this case), consumer needs and wants driving perception towards the brand (Wong, 2010). Brand image can be referred to as how students perceive education brand; however, brand identity is defined by student needs and wants that can explain how students desire to perceive education brand. Brand identity forms an important instrument of brand awareness based on the formation of brand image (Kuvykaite, Mascinskiene, 2010). Kapferer (1992) proposed that the brand identity prism is one of the most accepted models for brand identity; the prism proposes six aspects of brand identity: physique, personality, culture, self-image, reflection, and relationship for brands. This study extends Kapferer research work and proposes a brand equity model in the later section of this article.

2.10 Brand Promise and Brand Trust

Brand promise signifies the value of promoting the brand internally or externally and helps simplify the consumer (student) decision-making process (Judson et al., 2009). To achieve branding goals and brand recognition, institutes need to align their performances with external and internal brand promises (Jois, Chakrabarti, 2021). Synergies between stakeholders, infrastructure, physical landscape, opportunities at the city of study, communication, and promotion play a vital role in delivering the brand promise to achieve brand vision and strategy (Kavaratzis, 2007). Many faculty members feel institute should provide the necessary tools to deliver, also feel student engagement, promises grounded in reality, and communication to stakeholders is key to delivering on brand promise (Pringle, 2014). Brand trust signifies the intrinsic value of the brand that influences branding decisions and highlights the brand's believability to meet its promise (Jois, Chakrabarti, 2021). Brand trust significantly impacts brand equity (Gozukara, Colakoglu, 2016) and brand loyalty. Brand trust can also be defined as consumer experience (student experience or brand experience) regarding behavioral

traits, honesty, reliability, and credibility are the key elements underlying trust notion (Gozukara, Colakoglu, 2016). Brand trust defines the intention of consumers to purchase when there is not enough detail or information about new products or services being offered (Chaudhuri, Holbrook, 2001, Lau, Lee, 1999).

2.11 Brand Recognition

Brand recognition is turning out to be critical to the institute's global ranking, satisfaction among the student community (Ahmad, 2014) and word of mouth marketing (Jillapalli, Wilcox, 2010, Syed et al., 2016). Western higher education brands have experimented with learning methods, pedagogy, outcome-based teaching, technology, systems and processes to achieve global brand recognition (Iqbal et al., 2020). Globally educators can build brand recognition by focusing on pedagogy (Bodo, 2020), facilitation and learning methods (Anderson et al., 2018) and delivery of curriculum (Bodo, 2020), campus infrastructure (Jurse, 2011) and programmes & events at the campus (Syed et al., 2015, Swati, 2015). This study has adopted scales for brand recognition from various research works in marketing, such as Aaker (1991) work that defines the measure of brand recognition and brand strength involved in student consumer satisfaction, brand loyalty, and the consumer's brand relationships. Awareness, attitude, and usage metrics, known as AAU metrics, are used to measure brand recognition (Farris et al., 2010).

Brand salience is also one of the key measures of brand recognition, wherein two types of recall tests (aided and unaided recall) define salience (Hsia, 1988). Brand recognition is also measured using brand effects tests wherein brand association tests, brand attitude, brand image, brand dominance, brand value, and brand health are the key dimensions of the scale. Based on extensive and structured literature review, exploratory research, in-depth interviews with education sector experts, qualitative analysis of the open-ended, unstructured interviews, this study lists various objectives of the study as shown in the following section.

2. Objective

This study aims to study key attributes pertaining to select global management education brands and their globalization journey; the research will cover various aspects of the management education system globally in emerging markets like India (South Asia), South Eastern economies like Thailand, Indonesia and Malaysia, and part of Eastern Europe like Poland. An additional focus of the research was to analyze global students' perceptions of management education brands and identify basic attributes that play a key role in building global management education brands.

The objective of this article is also to build a global brand-building model and branding framework for management education.

3.1 Research questions

This study focuses on understanding global education brands from the perspective of students from emerging economy countries involved in the choice-making process while selecting higher education management brands. The focus of the study was on understanding the key attributes which play a major role for emerging economy management education brands. As the literature review highlighted a lack of academic work on higher education branding, not many researchers have tried to develop a model or framework for global higher education brands. Research questions of the study were as follows:

- Which antecedents influence students' choice-making process with respect to global education brands?
- What are the focus areas in building global education brands from the base of emerging markets?

3.2 Conceptual Framework

Brand awareness is a key to adding value that leads to sustainable competitive advantage, thus creating long-term sustainable value. Brand recognition is an important measure of brand equity (Tina, 2016) powered by brand strength which is based on customer (student) satisfaction, and increased customer brand relationships lead to brand loyalty (Aaker, 1991, Riccardo et al., 2017). Brand awareness (Tina, 2016) relates to functions of brand identities in consumers memory which can be measured by how consumers can identify the brand under various conditions (Keller and Kevin, 1993). Brand awareness is a key to understanding the consumer purchase decision process, based on strong brand awareness; a stronger predictor leads to brand success (Ya-Hsin et al., 2014). There are two types of brand recall ('unaided recall tests' and 'aided recall test') used to measure brand awareness thus brand recognition (Hsia, 1988).

Brand guidelines define rules and regulations throughout the experience, and student engagement enters into a critical phase when a prospective student takes up admission marking entry into the institution brand world. Brand awareness should be measured routinely to check the status of the brand promise, which impacts brand trust. The intrinsic value of the brand, believability of the brand to meet its promise signifies brand trust. Brand equity can be measured by awareness among prospective students (Tina, 2016), satisfaction, word of mouth among alumni and students, brand associations, the quality it delivers. Brand equity is the overall strength of the education

3.3 Research Model

Mechanisms are the ones wherein events such as higher student loyalty, positive word of mouth, student satisfaction (Anita, Kumar, 2017), better brand visibility are impact created under various conditions like excellence achieved by involving students in creating programs keeping in mind objects like industry, student, institution.

Student attitude towards management education impacts perception of the brand, as well it affects campus culture. Campus infrastructure is directly proportional to the way campus culture builds up. Scalability of infrastructure at campus results in a better culture campus, thus resulting in higher student satisfaction. Tougher selection mechanism results in a superior set of students' campuses resulting in an improved culture at the campus. Intellectual academic stimulation at campus brings in a blend of cultures at campus with diverse student backgrounds. Campus culture results in student satisfaction which in turn, coupled with student perception impacts student loyalty. Student satisfaction and student loyalty create brand recognition, as shown in figure 2 global education brand-building model.

Figure 2. Global Education Brand Building Model

3.3.1 Hypothesis

Student motivation and attitude play a major role in perception towards education brands leading to varied student loyalty, thus impacting brand recognition as stated in hypotheses H1. Scalable campus infrastructures lead to increased events at the campus, leading to improved culture, which drives satisfaction and loyalty towards higher education brands resulting in global recognition; therefore, authors state the hypothesis H2. Students' choice-making process defines the selection of institute & its campus; institute's student selection process defines the culture at a campus that

directly impacts student satisfaction and loyalty towards institutes, resulting in global brand recognition as mentioned in hypothesis H3. A stimulating academic environment at the campus, pedagogical content, rigorous curriculum drive culture at the campus, thus satisfaction levels at campus resulting in student loyalty and brand recognition for higher education brands resulting in hypothesis H4.

H1: Attitude will positively affect loyalty and brand recognition;

H2: Scalable infrastructure coupled with culture at campus leads to global brand recognition;

H3: Selection mechanism positively affects culture at campus, satisfaction and loyalty towards higher education brands resulting in global brand recognition;

H4: Academic rigor positively affects culture at campus and student satisfaction resulting in improved brand recognition.

3. Results

In this study, detailed literature reviews and expert opinions resulted in the identification of 29 attributes or key constructs, 51 measures of scale and 82 items for the measures. This study conducted structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis using IBM™ AMOSS™. By plotting histogram, researchers can see that data is normally distributed, so this study safely assumes that data is good to proceed with. As first 'Components Method of Extraction' was done to decide to reduce the number of variables. By conducting 'Exploratory Factor Analysis' using SPSS with an eigenvalue above 0.95 and by suppressing small coefficients below 0.299 as below this value will not be significant for grouping, factor loadings of 9-factor groupings as shown in Table 2 were achieved and 52 items which are key to the study was also identified as per Table 2. Further authors conducted 'component factor analysis' based on the initial computation of a complete table of intercorrelations among variables, also referred to as correlation matrix. The correlation matrix is then transformed by estimating factor model to obtain a factor matrix containing factor loadings for each variable, by analyzing either the Unrotated or Rotated Matrix representing the degrees of association which is a correlation of each variable with each factor while loadings take on a key role in the interpretation of the factors. Unrotated matrix shows that it did not maximize the loadings of each variable on one factor; thus, a rotation technique was applied to improve the interpretation through rotated factor matrix.

Table 2. Pattern Matrix–Brand Building Model

	Component								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Q9.1.2.Student Loyalty - Perceived performance			.893						
Q9.6.1.Global Recognition			.918						
Q2.6.2. Academic Performance–OO			.703						
Q4.2.1.WoM- Perception Learning			.832						
Q4.6. Brand Trust			.896						
Q1. Brand Recall						.622			
Q5.2. Brand Association						.918			
Q5.3. Brand Image						.504			
Q5.4. Brand Dominance						.673			
Q5.5. Brand Value						.958			
Q3.1 Gap: Expectation of performance								-.482	
Q3.2 Gap: Perceived experience of performance								-.536	
Q3.4 Affective aspects: Perception								-.531	
Q4.1 Perception- Learning								-.507	
Q4.3. Perception – Memory								-.553	
Q4.4.Perception - Attention – FIT								-.952	
Q4.5. Perception – Situation								-.514	
Q3.5 Attitude-Motivation	.585								
Q3.6.Expect Attitude Motivation	.975								
Q9.1.Student Loyalty - Perceived performance	.497								
Q9.2. Academic Freedom & Opportunity	.527								
Q9.3. Academic Freedom & Opportunity	.989								
Q9.5. Attitude - Opportunity – Tech	.506								
Q10.1. Migration to city	.505								
Q10.2. Placement, Career, Opportunity, Attitude	.547								
Q10.3. Attitude - Student - No force	.536								
Q10.4. Satisfaction - Attitude- Opportunity	.989								
Q3.1.1.Gap: Expectation of performance							.930		
Q3.3.1. Affective aspects: Attitude							.933		
Q3.4.1.Affective aspects: Perception							.930		
Q3.6.2.Expect Attitude Motivation							.917		
Q7.1.Culture at Campus- Over period of time-Team		.855							
Q7.3.Experience at campus & Culture		.833							
Q7.4.Culture, Value, Ethics		.824							
Q7.5.Innovation - Campus Culture		.968							
Q7.6.Support - Campus Culture		.959							
Q7.7.Safety & Stability at campus		.931							
Q7.8.Outcomes - Campus Culture		.924							
Q2.1 Academics Activities					.817				
Q2.6.Academic Performance–Outcome Orientation					.824				
Q9.1.1.Student Loyalty - Perceived performance					.808				
Q9.2.1.Academic Freedom & Opportunity					.820				
Q9.4. Academic Stimulus – Intellectual					.729				
Q2.2.InfrastructureFacilityAbilitytoExpand									.885
Q2.3.Place City Migration									.770
Q2.4.Global Opportunity - New Gen									.969
Q2.5.Diversity-Heterogenous systems									.803
Q8.1. Selection – Personality				.963					
Q8.2. Selection - Cognitive Ability				.997					
Q8.3. Selection - psychometric evaluations				.780					
Q8.5. Selection - scholarly performance				.773					
Q8.6. Selection - biographical data				.733					

Correlation matrix shows that correlations and most of communalities are greater than 0.5; hence these are good for analysis. Most of the communalities in the component matrix are above 0.7; however, few of the communalities were around 0.4, which authors decided to accept as the study is complex and has 80+ items & 50+ measures; all such select items were important for the field of study. By analyzing the 'Scree plot' as shown in figure 3 and drawing the line at an eigenvalue of 1 or 0.95, it was decided that 9 Factor groupings share more than half of the variance. This study concluded by looking at 'Scree Plot' that nine factors can represent a good model for the research objective as stated in the previous section.

Figure 3. Scree Plot –Brand Building Model

Authors further conducted structured equation modeling using AMOS to arrive at a brand-building model, as shown in figure 4. Correlation analysis (Gerald et al., 2003) of each of the linkages of the global brand building model as in figure 2 concluded that all the relationships are significant at $p < .001$, and all are positive. Most of the P values are below 0.001, and two values are positive and below 0.05, as shown in 'Regression Weights' Table 3, which shows that relationships are significant.

Figure 4. SEM Model – Global Brand Building Model

Table 3. Regression Weights

		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
CampusCulture	AcademicStimulus	0.638	0.32	1.992	0.046
CampusCulture	CampusInfrastructureScalability	0.657	0.14	4.782	***
CampusCulture	SelectMechanism	0.09	0.04	2.304	0.021
Perception	Attitude	1.879	0.07	26.01	***
StudentSatisfaction	CampusCulture	0.766	0.03	27.7	***
StudentLoyalty	StudentSatisfaction	0.472	0.02	27.33	***
StudentLoyalty	Perception	0.074	0.01	6.637	***
BrandRecognition	StudentLoyalty	0.384	0.04	9.313	***
BrandRecognition	StudentSatisfaction	0.151	0.02	9.782	***
Q2.2.InfrastructureFacilityAbilitytoExpand	CampusInfrastructureScalability	0.976	0.03	33.5	***
Q2.3.PlaceCityMigration	CampusInfrastructureScalability	0.958	0.03	32.93	***
Q2.4.GlobalOpportunityNewGen	CampusInfrastructureScalability	0.995	0.03	33.65	***
Q8.1.SelectionPersonality	SelectMechanism	1			
Q8.2.SelectionCognitiveAbility	SelectMechanism	1.022	0.03	31.56	***
Q8.5.Selectionscholarlyperformance	SelectMechanism	1.01	0.03	31.62	***
Q8.3.Selectionpsychometricreevaluations	SelectMechanism	1.011	0.03	31.63	***
Q8.6.Selectionbiographicaldata	SelectMechanism	1.022	0.03	31.64	***
Q9.4.AcademicStimulusIntellectual	AcademicStimulus	1.565	0.07	21.71	***
Q2.6.AcademicPerformanceOO	AcademicStimulus	1.598	0.07	21.78	***
Q9.2.1.AcademicFreedomampOpportunity	AcademicStimulus	1			
Q3.6.ExpectAttitudeMotivation	Attitude	1			
Q3.5AttitudeMotivation	Attitude	1.022	0.04	25.91	***
Q9.1.StudentLoyaltyPerceeedperformance	Attitude	0.994	0.04	25.57	***
Q9.2.AcademicFreedomampOpportunity	Attitude	0.975	0.04	25.43	***
Q9.3.AcademicFreedomampOpportunity	Attitude	0.916	0.04	24.37	***
Q9.5.AttitudeOpportunityTech	Attitude	1.01	0.04	25.92	***
Q10.1.Migrationtocity	Attitude	0.913	0.04	24.4	***
Q10.2.PlacementCareerOpportunityAttitude	Attitude	0.969	0.04	25.19	***
Q10.3.AttitudeStudentNoforce	Attitude	1.021	0.04	25.82	***
Q10.4.SatisfactionAttitudeOpportunity	Attitude	0.977	0.04	25.14	***
Q7.6.SupportCampusCulture	CampusCulture	1			
Q7.5.InnovationCampusCulture	CampusCulture	1.021	0.03	32.28	***
Q7.4.CultureValueEthics	CampusCulture	1.004	0.03	32.05	***
Q7.3.ExperienceatCampusampCulture	CampusCulture	0.997	0.03	31.92	***
Q7.7.SafetypStabilityatcampus	CampusCulture	1.007	0.03	32.08	***
Q7.1.CultureatCampusOverperiodoftime	CampusCulture	1.001	0.03	32.1	***
Q7.8.OutcomesCampusCulture	CampusCulture	1.009	0.03	32.15	***
Q4.1PerceptionLearning	Perception	1			
Q4.3.PerceptionMemory	Perception	0.948	0.03	27.69	***
Q3.1GapExpectationofperformance	Perception	0.999	0.04	28.18	***
Q3.2GapPerceivedexperienceofperformance	Perception	0.967	0.04	27.73	***
Q3.4AffectiveaspectsPerception	Perception	0.961	0.04	27.56	***
Q4.4.PeceptionAttentionFIT	Perception	0.64	0.02	33.63	***
Q4.5.PerceptionSituation	Perception	0.936	0.04	26.93	***
Q9.1.1.StudentLoyaltyPerceeedperformance	AcademicStimulus	0.639	0.04	17.49	***
Q3.4.1.AffectiveaspectsPerception	StudentSatisfaction	1.108	0.01	96	***
Q3.6.2.ExpectAttitudeMotivation	StudentSatisfaction	0.916	0.02	56.04	***
Q3.3.1.AffectiveaspectsAttitude	StudentSatisfaction	1.021	0.01	81.39	***
Q3.1.1.GapExpectationofperformance	StudentSatisfaction	1			
Q9.1.2.StudentLoyaltyPerceeedperformance	StudentLoyalty	2.422	0.06	37.9	***
Q9.6.1.GlobalRecognition	StudentLoyalty	1.715	0.06	30.67	***
Q2.6.2.AcademicPerformanceOO	StudentLoyalty	1.284	0.04	30.78	***
Q4.2.1.WoMPerceptionLearning	StudentLoyalty	1.348	0.04	34.04	***
Q4.6.BrandTrust	StudentLoyalty	1			
Q5.5.BrandValue	BrandRecognition	1			
Q5.4.BrandDominance	BrandRecognition	2.208	0.12	17.92	***
Q5.3.BrandImage	BrandRecognition	0.734	0.04	17.78	***
Q5.2.BrandAssociation	BrandRecognition	0.678	0.04	16.97	***
Q1.BrandRecall	BrandRecognition	2.079	0.12	17.36	***
Q2.1AcademicsActivities	AcademicStimulus	0.523	0.03	18.15	***
Q2.5.DiversityHetrogenoussystem	CampusInfrastructureScalability	1			

The Cronbach Alpha for all variables are as shown in Table 4, was above 0.7 (most were above 0.9, 90% variability), which means more than 70% of the variability in a composite score while combining scales (adapted scales from Likert scale) is true score variance which means also is reliable or internally consistent reliable variable. The inter-item correlation matrix shows that all the variables items in the table are positively associated, which confirms the model fit. This study adopted the 'Likert Scale' for selection mechanism wherein 'Cronbach's Alpha' after deleting one variable is not higher than the original 0.7, which means we are not having any redundancy. All the composite reliability scores are analogous with Cronbach alpha and more than the minimum required 0.7. To make sure the model fits well, the 'Regression Analysis' with 'enter method' was undertaken to ensure that model fits well. The F value was also checked, and significance was below 0.001 to ensure these factors represent the true model.

Table 4. Reliability Statistics – all Variables

Scale	Scale Factor Grouping Name	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
Component 3	Student Loyalty	.904	.908	5
Component 6	Brand Recognition	.745	.809	5
Component 8	Perception	.755	.764	7
Component 1	Attitude	.876	.886	10
Component 7	Student Satisfaction	.959	.959	4
Component 2	Campus Culture	.959	.963	7
Component 5	Academic Stimulus	.855	.855	5
Component 9	Campus Infrastructure Scalability	.904	.910	4
Component 4	Selection Mechanism	.902	.912	5

Regression analysis with enter methods resulted in R value above 0.7 and R Square above 60% with a significance value below 0.05 which means that independent variables are a significant predictor of dependent variables that shows models fits well. The AVE average variance extracted varies from 0.5 to 0.7, wherein the minimum recommended is 0.5 (Fornell, Larcker, 1981); thus, all attributes demonstrate good internal consistency and reliability. The overall significance of the correlation matrix was assessed with the 'KMO and Bartlett Test' and the factorability of the comprehensive set of variables, the individual variables using the 'Measure of Sampling Adequacy' (MSA). Bartlett's test finds that the correlations, when taken collectively, are significant at the 0.0001 level, 'MSA' also looks at the pattern between variables; overall, MSA falls above 0.5 with a determinant at 2.1.

As construct reliability (CR), most latent variable results values are above 0.9, and all variables (instruments) values are above 0.7; hence study can conclude that 'Convergent Validity' is satisfied. The 'Discriminant Validity' test results in Table 5 demonstrate that Wilks' Lambda is statistically significant and variance between all is above 0.644. Each of the variance extracted and variance between all is significantly

higher than the correlation square percentage; hence, discriminant validity is satisfied for each variable. As both convergent validity and discriminant validity are satisfied hence the study can safely assume that this research has better construct validity.

Table 5. Discriminant Validity Test Table

Factor Grouping Name	Average Loading	Variance Extracted	Variance Between All	Correlation	Correlation Square
Student Loyalty	0.848	0.720	64%	.247	6.1%
Brand Recognition	0.735	0.540		.331	11.0%
Perception	-0.582	0.339		.048	0.2%
Attitude	0.666	0.443		.203	4.1%
Student Satisfaction	0.928	0.861		.267	7.1%
Campus Culture	0.899	0.808		.169	2.9%
Academic Stimulus	0.800	0.640		.257	6.6%
Campus Infrastructure Scalability	0.856	0.734		.316	10.0%
Selection Mechanism	0.849	0.721		.268	7.2%

All CR of latent attributes are reliable; thus, this study can say that the proposed SEM model is valid and can be accepted as overall model fitness is proven in Table 6 that shows NFI, RFI, IFI, TLI, CFI (Taewon and Karen, 2008) are 0.91 or greater. Global brand building model fitness can also be proved by referring to Table 7 that shows CMIN/DF as 4.867, which is below the acceptable value of 5.0. Parsimony adjusted measures are above 0.8 as per Table 8, which demonstrates model fitness. By referring to Table 9, brand building model fitness can be proven as RMSEA value is 0.035, which is well below the acceptable value of 0.05, and PCLOSE value is 1.00.

Table 6. SEM Model Fit Table

Model	NFI Delta1	RFI rho1	IFI Delta2	TLI rho2	CFI
Default model	.920	.912	.936	.929	.935
Saturated model	1.000		1.000		1.000
Independence model	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

Table 7. CMIN/DF Model Fit Table

Model	NPAR	CMIN	DF	P	CMIN/DF
Default model	184	6064.058	1246	.000	4.867
Saturated model	1430	.000	0		
Independence model	52	76011.443	1378	.000	55.161

Table 8. Parsimony Adjusted Measures Model Fit Table

Model	PRATIO	PNFI	PCFI
Default model	.904	.832	.846
Saturated model	.000	.000	.000
Independence model	1.000	.000	.000

Table 9. RMSEA/PCLOSE Measures Model Fit Table

Model	RMSEA	LO 90	HI 90	PCLOSE
Default model	.035	.034	.035	1.000
Independence model	.129	.128	.130	.000

5. Analysis

This study utilized the scales, measures and items of the branding model to validate the constructs of branding framework and correlation analysis of each of the linkages of global brand building model as shown in figure 2 and branding framework of figure 1 resulted in the conclusion that all the relationships are significant. This study concludes that student needs and wants drive perception while making the choice of an institute for their higher education; similarly, both student need and want results in the selection of brand based on the promise made by brands that consequently defines the identity of the brand. Brand identity and promise are critical to student experience during the choice-making process, which sequentially sets expectations for the post-purchase experience phase. Students tend to compare experience at campus with the promise made during the choice-making process and perception of the brand based on its brand identity. Consequently, propositions P1 and P2 cannot be rejected. Propositions P3 and P4 state that students' experience while choosing higher education institute, student onboarding experience at the campus, life at campus and institute way of handling alumni is directly proportional to brand trust and brand awareness. Based on correlation analyses, P3 and P4 cannot be rejected statistically, except for the fact that trust in brand also positively impacts brand awareness which emanated from expert interviews. By examining all correlations between brand trust, brand awareness and brand equity, this study concluded that all relationships are highly significant at $p < .01$ and r and below 0.4; based on these findings, propositions P4 cannot be rejected that state trust in brand impacts brand equity similarly awareness towards brand build equity when coupled with trust towards the brand.

'Exploratory Factor Analysis' resulted in 9-factor groupings. Principal component factor analysis based on correlation matrix along with 'Scree plot' confirmed 9 Factor groupings share more than half of variance and are good for analysis. This study assumption was validated with exogenous variables being attitude, infrastructure scalability, selection mechanism and academic stimulus, endogenous variables being perception, campus culture, student loyalty, student satisfaction and dependent variable brand recognition.

By analyzing the results presented in the previous section, the path coefficients resulting from structured equation modeling, this study concludes that hypothesis H1 is supported. Student positive attitude towards education institutes significantly improves loyalty towards brand thus resulting in global recognition especially if the higher

education institute has global presence resulting in attracting global student community. Most of the expert interviews also confirm hypothesis H1. By analyzing the intensity of the coefficients of each relationship, This study can safely state that hypothesis H2 is also confirmed, campus infrastructure that adheres to global standards leads to the superior quality of events and culture at the campus, resulting in improvised student satisfaction and loyalty driving global brand recognition however expert interviews had divided opinion on the effect of campus infrastructure on global brand recognition, some expert opined that campus infrastructure, events, culture plays a key role in student loyalty and few academicians experts felt that infrastructure only has moderating effect not significant effect on global recognition.

Further analysis established that hypothesis H3 can also be confirmed as higher education institutes with better selection mechanisms and global student community choice-making processes positively influences campus culture, consequently impacting student satisfaction and loyalty, resulting in a directly proportional relationship with global brand recognition. Most education experts feel that selection is key to student quality, professing quality, events, and culture at the campus. Thus, combining these factors influences student satisfaction and loyalty, resulting in word of mouth across the globe through various mediums, thus driving global brand recognition.

Based on eighteen expert interviews, this study states that directors of higher education institutes and vice-chancellors of universities feel that academic rigour attracts the global student community; however, based on SEM analysis and intensity of coefficients, H4 is not completely supported. Academic rigor and curriculum depth positively impact student satisfaction; however, student satisfaction does not improve brand recognition significantly based on the strength of the linkage. This study also highlights that student satisfaction positively impacts student loyalty; if student loyalty is high, then brand recognition among the student & alumni community will be very high. Thus, hypothesis H4 can also be understood as academic activities that aid and give impetus to events at campus result in improved student satisfaction similarly academic depth and professing quality positively impacts student satisfaction driving student loyalty that in turn positively influence brand recognition. Similarly, this study also reveals that scalable campus infrastructure plays a vital role in events at the campus, resulting in improved culture, resulting in increased student satisfaction; thus, student loyalty positively impacts brand recognition. However, based on the strength of the relationship between student screening & selection mechanism and campus culture, this study concludes that selection mechanism plays a role in culture at the campus but is not very significant in defining culture, satisfaction, loyalty among students. Thus, the conclusion can be drawn that selection mechanism does impact brand recognition but not significantly.

5. Conclusion

Student needs, student wants, and attitude towards higher education institutions lead to either positive or negative perceptions towards education brand. Student attitude towards various aspects leads to perception towards education brand leading to diverse student experience and student loyalty impacting brand recognition. Scalable campus infrastructure with a large geographical presence based on various facilities results in improved campus culture. Some of the key characteristics of efficient campus infrastructure are large classrooms fitted with efficient technology, infrastructure catering to varied sports and fun related activities, campus festivals, hostels within the campus, large diversified food facilities. All these factors create a unique campus culture that is particular to that institution resulting in unique brand identity and brand equity, thus impacting student satisfaction resulting in loyalty and brand recognition. Student selection mechanism in any university is a key to building a particular culture at the campus that can be powered by financial aids, scholarships to well-deserving students. Students with diversified backgrounds being encouraged during the selection process influence culture at campus leading to satisfaction among students, thus resulting in positive word of mouth and loyalty, sequentially enabling brand recognition, as shown in figure 2. Various academic activities act as stimuli for student brains leading to positive word of mouth among students, creating a positive campus culture leading to satisfaction among students resulting in loyalty thus global brand recognition. In some cases, academic rigour creates satisfaction among students by recognizing their previously made choice for selecting a particular education brand.

6. Contributions of the study and Future directions

This study is limited to a few emerging economies and western countries, and researchers can adopt this study to expand into diverse developing countries and cover a wider geographical base. The contributions of the study are that most of the studies in branding are limited to a few aspects of the brand; this study covers wider aspects of branding. This study brings out a unique branding framework that researchers can empirically validate in their respective spear of research on branding. The authors also bring out a global brand building model and brand recognition model encompassing the consumer (students) perspective. Authors' proposed framework and model are unique in the higher education sector because it covers wider aspects of student, campus & infrastructure, academics, culture, attitude, perception, selection mechanism, and loyalty. Higher education marketers can refer to the global brand-building model while taking their brands global. Researchers who work on wider consumer studies can adapt the model and framework from this study to test the validity of their research. The framework as in figure 1 and model in figure 2 may apply beyond the higher education sector to wider marketing and branding areas that need to be empirically validated.

References

- Aaker, A., & David. (1991). *Managing Brand Equity under What is Brand Equity? Section*. Simon and Schuster. ISBN 9781439188385.
- Ackerman, Phillip L., & Maynard G. (1994). Typical Intellectual Engagement and Personality, Reply to Rocklin. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 86 (1): pg. 150–153. Doi:10.1037/0022-0663.86.1.150.
- Ahmad, S. (2014). Evaluating student satisfaction of quality at international branch campuses. *Assessment and Evaluation in Higher Education*, Vol. 40, No. 4, pp. 488-507.
- Ajzen, I. (1985). From intentions to actions: A theory of planned behavior. In *J. Kuhl and J. Beckmann (Eds.)*. Action control: From cognition to behavior.
- Alan, S., & Gary, J. (2011). *Perception, Attribution, and Judgment of Others, Organizational Behaviour: Understanding and Managing Life at Work*. Vol.7.
- American Marketing Association. (2017). *Definitions of Marketing*. Retrieved from <https://www.ama.org/the-definition-of-marketing-what-is-marketing/> (accessed on 8th October 2021)
- Anderson, L., Hibbert, P., Mason, K., & Rivers, C. (2018). Management Education in Turbulent Times. *Journal of Management Education*, 1–18
- Anil, N.K., & Icli, G.E. (2013). MBA Students' Satisfaction and Loyalty: State vs. Private Universities in Turkey. *Trziste / Market*, Vol. Xxv (2013), Br. 2, Str. 177–198.
- Anita, P., & Kumar, V. (2017). Customer engagement: the construct, antecedents, and consequences. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 45:294–311.
- Bartlett, C., A., & Ghoshal, S. (2000). Going Global: Lessons from Late Movers. *Harvard Business Review*, March-April 2000, pp. 132–142.
- Berry, L.L., & Parasuraman, A. (1991). *Marketing Services: Competing Through Quality*. New York: Free Press, ISBN 978-0-02-903079-0.
- Bodo, B.S. (2020). Why Business Schools Need Radical Innovations: Drivers and Development Trajectories, *Journal of Marketing Education*, Vol. 42(2), 93–107.
- Chapleo, C. (2015). An exploration of branding approaches in UK universities. *International Journal of Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Marketing*. February 2015.
- Chaudhuri, A., & Holbrook, M.B. (2001). The chain of effects from brand trust and brand affect to brand performance: The role of brand loyalty. *Journal of Marketing*, 65(2), 81–93.
- Chinta, R., Mansureh, K., & Janelle, E. (2016). A conceptual framework for evaluating higher education institutions. *International Journal of Educational Management*, Vol. 30 Iss 6.
- Cova, & Bernard. (1997). Continuity and Consumption: Towards a Detailing of the 'Linking Value' of Product or Services. *European Journal of Marketing*, 31(3–4), 297–316.

- Dao, Mai Thi Ngoc, & Thorpe, A. (2015). What factors influence Vietnamese students' choice of university? *International Journal of Educational Management*, Vol. 29, Iss 5 pp. 666–681.
- Dawar, N., & Frost, T. (1999). Competing with Giants: Survival Strategies for Local Companies in Emerging Markets. *Magazine. Harvard Business Review*, March-April, 1999.
- Delaney, J.A., & Doyle, W.R. (2011). State Spending on Higher Education: Testing the Balance Wheel over Time. *Journal of Education Finance*, 36(4), 343–368. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23018116>
- Drewes, Torben, & Michael, C. (2006). How Do Students Choose a University?: An Analysis of Applications to Universities in Ontario, Canada. *Research in Higher Education*, Vol. 47, No. 7 (Nov 2006), pp.781–800.
- Fabio Vinicius de Macedo Bergamo, Antonio Carlos Giuliani, Silvia Helena Carvalho, Ramos Valladão de Camargo, Felipe Zambaldi, Mateus Canniatti Ponchio. (2012). Student loyalty based on relationship quality: an analysis on higher education institutions. *Brazilian Business Review, Vitória*, v. 9, n. 2, Art.2, p.26–46, apr–jun 2012.
- Farris, Paul W, Neil T, Bendle, Phillip E. Pfeifer, & David J. Reibstein. (2010). Marketing Metrics: The Definitive Guide to Measuring Marketing Performance. *Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Pearson Education, Inc.* ISBN 0-13-705829-2.
- Fazio, R.H. (1986). How do attitudes guide behavior? In R. M. Sorrentino and E. T. Higgins (Eds.). *The handbook of motivation and cognition: Foundations of social behavior*. pp 204–243, New York: Guilford Press.
- Fishbein, Martin. (1967). *A behavior theory approach to the relations between beliefs about an object and the attitude toward the object, Readings in attitude theory and measurement*. New York: John Wiley and Sons, pp. 389-400.
- Fishbein, Martin, and Icek Ajzen. (1975). *Belief, Attitude, Intention and Behavior*. Addison-Wesley.
- Fornell, Claes, & David F. Larcker. (1981). Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18: pp39–50.
- Reichheld, F. (1996). *The Loyalty Effect*.
- Gatfield, T., Barker, M., & Graham, P. (1999). Measuring communication impact for university advertising materials. *Corporate Communications: An international Journal*, Vol. 4 No. 2, pp.73–79.
- Gatfield, Terry & Ching-huei Chen. (2006). Measuring Student Choice Criteria Using the Theory of Planned Behaviour: The Case of Taiwan, Australia, UK, and USA. *Journal of Marketing for Higher Education*, 16:1, 77–95, DOI: 10.1300/J050v16n01_04.
- Gerald Albaum, David K. Tse, George C. Hozier Jr., & Kenneth G. Baker.(2003). Extending Marketing Activities and Strategies from Domestic to Foreign Markets. *Journal of Global Marketing*, 16:3, 105–129.

- Goff, Maynard, & Phillip L. Ackerman. (1992). Personality-Intelligence relations: assessment of typical intellectual engagement. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 84 (4): 537–552.
- Gozukara, I., & Colakoglu, N. (2016). A Research on Generation Y Students: Brand Innovation, Brand Trust and Brand Loyalty. *International Journal of Business Management and Economic Research (IJBMER)*, Vol 7(2), 2016, 603–611.
- Hesham El-Rewini & Mostafa Abd-El-Barr. (2005). *Advanced Computer Architecture and Parallel Processing*. John Wiley and Sons, p. 66, ISBN 978-0-471-47839-3.
- Hsia, H.J. (1988). *Mass Communications Research Methods: A Step-by-Step Approach*. Routledge.
- Hulten, B. (2017). Branding by the five senses: A sensory branding framework. *Journal of Brand Strategy*, Vol.6, No.3, winter 2017–18
- Ilie, C., Fornes, G., Cardoza, G., & Quintana, J.C.M. (2020). Development of Business Schools in Emerging Markets: *Learning through Adoption and Adaptation, Sustainability*, 12, 8448. Doi: 10.3390/su12208448
- Iqbal, M.J., Rasli, A.B., & Hassan. I. (2020). University Branding: A Myth or a Reality. *Pak. J. Commer. Soc. Sci.*, 2012, Vol. 6 (1), 168–184.
- James A. Muncy. (2008). The orientation evaluation matrix (OEM): Are students customers or products? *Marketing Education Review*, Volume 18, Number 3 (Fall 2008).
- Jois, A., & Chakrabarti, S. (2021). Globalization Journey of Brand by Creating Experience Wave. *Academy of Marketing Studies Journal*, Volume 25, Issue 5.
- Judson, K.M., Aurand, T.W., Gorchels, L., & Gordon, G.L. (2009). Building a University Brand from Within: University Administrators' Perspectives of Internal Branding. *Services Marketing Quarterly*, 30:54–68.
- Jurse, M. (2011). A Market Perspective of Aligning University, Business Education in Transition Countries with the Emerging Globalisation of Higher Education. *Transformations in Business and Economics*, Vol. 10, No. 2 (23), pp.104–124.
- Kapferer, J.N. (1992). *Strategic Brand Management*. Kogan Page: London, 1992
- Kavaratzis, M. (2007). Cities and their brands: Lessons from corporate branding. *Place Branding and Public Diplomacy*, 5, 26 – 37. doi: 10.1057/pb.2008.3.
- Kessler, Sheila. (2003). *Customer satisfaction toolkit for ISO 9001:2000*. Milwaukee, Wis.: ASQ Quality Press. ISBN 0-87389-559-2.
- Keller, & Kevin, L. (1993). Conceptualizing, Measuring, and Managing Customer-Based Brand Equity. *Journal of Marketing*, 57 (1), pp 1–22. Doi:10.2307/1252054, ISSN 0022-2429, JSTOR 1252054.
- Kirkpatrick, D.L., & Kirkpatrick, J.D. (1994). *Evaluating Training Programs*. Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
- Kuvykaite, R., & Mascinskiene, J. (2010). Transformation of a National Brand into an International Brand. *Inzinerine Ekonomika-Engineering Economics*, 21(4), 446–455.

- Lau, G.T., & Lee, S.H. (1999). Consumers trust in a brand and the link to brand loyalty. *Journal of Market-Focused Management*, 4(4): 341–370.
- Levitt, T. (1983). The Globalization of Markets. Magazine. *Harvard Business Review*, May, 1983.
- Martin, M.C., Moriuchi, E., Ronda, M.S., Jill, D.M., & Charlene, N. (2015). The Importance of University Traditions and Rituals in Building Alumni Brand Communities and Loyalty. *International Academy of Marketing Studies Journal*, Volume 19, Number 3.
- Pringle, J.D. (2014). *Faculty Perception of Branding – A Multi-case Qualitative Study*. DBA Thesis, University of Bath, October, 2014.
- QS Global MBA Rankings. (2019). *Annual Report*. Retrieved from <https://www.qs.com/rankings/> (accessed on 20 December 2020).
- Ramzan, M. (2015). University Evaluation: an important indicator towards quality in higher education. *Journal of Research in Social Sciences-JRSS*, Vol.3 No.1, pp. 2306–112X.
- Riccardo, R., Lamberto, Z., Massimiliano, M.P., & Cristiano, C. (2017). Exploring the Antecedents of Brand Loyalty and Electronic Word of Mouth in Social-Media-Based Brand Communities: Do Gender Differences Matter? *Journal of Global Marketing*, 30:3, 147-160. DOI: 10.1080/08911762.2017.1306899
- Ross, Edward, Alsworth. (1902). Recent tendencies in Sociology – II. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, Pg.82-110
- Schacter, D.L., Gilbert, D.T., & Wegner, D.M. (2011). *Psychology (2nd Edition)*. New York: Worth.
- Stone, B.E. (2012). Experience, Problematization, and the Question of the Contemporary. *The Pluralist*, Vol. 7, No. 3 (Fall 2012), pp. 44–50.
- Syed, Zamberi, Ahmad & Frederick, Robert, Buchanan. (2015). Motivation factors in students decision to study at international branch campuses in Malaysia. *Studies in Higher Education*. DOI:10.1080/03075079.2015.1067604.
- Syed Zamberi Ahmad, Robert Buchanan, F., & Norita Ahmad. (2016). Examination of students' selection criteria for international education. *International Journal of Educational Management*, Vol. 30 Issue 6, pp.1088–1103.
- Taewon, Suh and Karen H. Smith. (2008). Attitude toward Globalization and Country-of-Origin Evaluations: Toward a Dynamic Theory. *Journal of Global Marketing*, 21:2, 127-139. DOI: 10.1080/08911760802135202
- Teng, & Ssu-yu. (1943). Chinese Influence on The Western Examination System. *Harvard Journal of Asiatic Studies*, 7 (4): 267-312. Doi: 10.2307/2717830. ISSN 0073-0548, JSTOR 2717830.
- Tina, Vukasovic. (2016). An Empirical Investigation of Brand Equity: A Cross-Country Validation Analysis. *Journal of Global Marketing*. DOI:10.1080/08911762.2016.1194508
- Turner. (1893). *The Significance of the Frontier in American History*. American Historical Association U.S. Department of Labor Employment and Training

- Administration 1999 report. Retrieved from <https://www.doleta.gov> (accessed on 20th December 2020).
- Von Stumm, Sophie, Hell, Benedikt, Chamorro-Premuzic, & Tomas. (2011). The Hungry Mind: Intellectual Curiosity Is the Third Pillar of Academic Performance. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 6 (6): 574–588.
Doi:10.1177/1745691611421204.
- Wilkins, S., LanHe, Li Zhu, & Elmoshnb, M. (2018). The resilience of the MBA in emerging economies: student motivations for wanting an MBA in China and the United Arab Emirates. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*. DOI:10.1080/1360080X.2018.1462439
- Werner, R., & Kumar, V. (2002). The mismanagement of customer loyalty. *Harvard Business Review*, 80 (7): 86–95. PMID 12140857.
- Wong, J. (2010). Using a Brand Identity Index for Relevancy in Teaching Collegiate Marketing. *The Journal of Applied Business and Economics*.
- Woo, S.E., Harms, P.D., & Kuncel, N.R. (2007). *Integrating personality and intelligence: Typical intellectual engagement and need for cognition*. *Personality and Individual Differences*. 43 (6): 1635–1639.
- Ya-Hsin, H., Ya-hei, H., Suh-Yueh, C., & Wenchang, F. (2014). Is Brand Awareness a Marketing Placebo. *International Journal of Business and Information*, 9 (1), pp. 29–60.